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PROBLEMS OF FOREST MANAGEMENT IN ABAY REGION

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Abstract

The energy necessary for life comes to Earth mainly in the form of solar radiation, which is used by green plants for photosynthesis, and from them goes further into food chains, and therefore controls biogeochemical cycles. In addition, solar energy determines the climatic zonality of the planet and ocean currents, i.e. directly affects the habitat of living beings. Humanity satisfies its needs through various activities. Modern economic activity leads to significant negative changes in the environment. The reality of today has become global environmental problems that threaten the very existence of mankind. The most important reasons for their occurrence are considered to be the growth of the population of the Earth and an unprecedented increase in the scale of production.

Keywords: pine forest, Abay region, forest management, Semey ormany.

The problem of human interaction with nature is an eternal and modern problem at the same time. After all, humanity is connected with the natural environment by its origin, existence and future. Man is an element of nature, part of a complex nature-society system. Mankind satisfies many of its needs (biological, resource, spiritual) at the expense of nature. The natural environment creates conditions for human life as a biological species; components of the natural environment are used in human economic activity. Nature is a source of satisfaction of his aesthetic needs [1, 2]

The reserves of the most valuable tree species, such as fir, cedar, larch and spruce, are mainly concentrated in the Abay region of the region .

Abay region is the largest industrial region of the republic. Powerful enterprises of the mining and metallurgical industries function here; the largest factories for the production of non-ferrous and rare metals.

During the period of intensive development of non-ferrous metallurgy (1940-1950) in East Kazakhstan, the base of the construction industry was formed, which is currently represented by the trusts "Altai-svinetsstroy", "Leningorsk-svinetsstroy", "Zyryanovskstroy" with their own basic enterprises in all industrial zones of the region. To this should be added building materials enterprises: a cement plant, a

plant for non-metallic and road-building materials, and brick factories. The energy industry of the region is formed locally for each industrial region by a network of thermal power plants, industrial and regional boiler houses, as well as hydroelectric power plants along the Irtysh River (Bukhtarminskaya , Ust-Kamenogorsk), which together meets the needs of industry and the population in the heating system, electricity. Moreover, up to 70% of the heat carrier energy is directed to the needs of industry.

million m³ of wastewater enters water bodies and drains, and about one billion tons of solid waste has accumulated in various storage facilities. The processed ores contain other elements besides lead, zinc, and copper. There are also sources of lithium, thallium, niobium, beryllium, etc. In a word, about 100 pollutants are registered in the air, water and soil of the region.

Moreover, the content of these toxicants exceeds the norm by 1.5-5 times for thallium, beryllium, zinc, copper, 10 or more times for boron, lead, chromium, vanadium, nickel, and aluminum.

Along with this, in many industrial regions of the Abai region, there is an unfavorable radiation situation. Long-term observations of the sanitary and epidemiological service over the radiation background of the region's territory showed that the population was exposed

to the dangerous effects of ground and air explosions carried out at the Semipalatinsk (from 1948 to 1990) and Lob Norsk test sites. Radioactive substances, such as strontium - 90, iodine - 131, cesium - 137, selenium - 144, plutonium - 239, are found in soil, water, and plants. Moreover, the intensity of their distribution is global. In 60% of samples of bottom sediments of the rivers of the Irtysh basin, lakes Markakol and Zaisan, pesticides were noted, sometimes in very high concentrations: HCCH - 2.2; DDT - 0.6; 2.4D - 0.6 mg / kg, occasionally nitran - 0.6 mg / kg. The defeat by pesticides is mainly associated with irrigated agriculture in Prizeisan.

The forest is continuously undergoing change as a result of the impact of natural and anthropogenic factors. Some of these changes can lead to serious disturbances in the structure of forest biogeocenoses. The most negative of these factors are: uncontrolled human activity, the activity of insect pests, forest fires, etc. [3].

Under conditions of intensive resource development, the areas of typical landscapes that perform important environmental functions are shrinking. To justify the need for their inclusion in the ecological framework of the territory as key landscape areas, the first task is to conduct an inventory that objectively reflects their state and specifics of spatial distribution.

At present, the deterioration of forest ecosystems under the influence of various anthropogenic and natural factors is an urgent problem. First of all, the forest was considered by man mainly as a source of raw materials, which should have some economic indicators. Thus, felling, regulated by timber harvesting, is an integral part of the existence of any forestry. In modern conditions, the world is reevaluating views on the importance of the forest and recognizing its leading role among the components of the biosphere, which necessitates the improvement of the forest management system and its reorientation towards increasing the ecological significance of forests [4].

The protection of forests from unauthorized logging and hunting on the territory of the Semey Ormany SFNR is carried out by the service for the protection of natural complexes and objects, as well as state inspectors directly on the territory of the reserve. The entire area of the protected area is divided into quarters, the average area of which is 100 hectares. The quarters are assigned state inspectors who constantly monitor their condition. Checkpoints are under 24-hour surveillance. The territory of the reserve is periodically patrolled by operational groups. A plan for joint operational work with local law enforcement agencies was developed and agreed with the akims of the districts and the city of Semey.

The meaning of recreational resources lies in the quality of forest biogeocenosis, which can influence the restoration of the physical, spiritual, moral and emotional forces of a person lost in the process of labor activity [5]. It is obvious that the forest user, as well as the recreant, is less interested in the issue of timber stock in the forest area used for recreational activities than the quality of the natural landscape and the leisure potential in this area.

Thinning is the most important forest management activity aimed at improving and enhancing the environment-forming role of forest plantations under these conditions [6]. Despite the special position of the natural reserve, along with sanitary cuttings, illegal cuttings take place every year. Since the establishment of the state forest natural reserve GLPR "Semey Ormany" for the period 2003 - 2013, by a court decision on the facts of illegal logging, 735 violators were brought to administrative responsibility, with fines in the amount of 10 million 305 thousand tenge, 89 criminal cases were initiated, 688 violators were charged with damages in the amount of 56 million 590 thousand tenge [7].

The volume of illegally felled trees for the period 2010-2012 and for the first half of 2013 amounted to 2.7 thousand cubic meters, 17.2 million tenge was damaged, of which only 2.6 million were compensated. Only during the audit The prosecutor's office revealed 15 facts of illegal felling of 1153 pine trees, with a total volume of more than 150 cubic meters. m. with damage in the amount of 1 million 664 thousand 407 tenge. In 2013, 10 cases of illegal logging were detected, with a total volume of cut wood of 239 cubic meters, with an amount of damage of 1 million 811 thousand tenge. For the period from 2017 to 2019, 382 offenses were registered, 15 facts of illegal logging were revealed. In 2021, 49 facts of illegal cutting of trees and shrubs were revealed, on which 6 pre-trial investigations were launched and 43 violators were brought to administrative responsibility [8].

Most of the environmentally oriented research and practical developments in forest management planning in the forested countries of the temperate zone are, of course, aimed at the conservation and restoration of biodiversity. In contrast to the landscape-geographical approach in Canada, the role of a person is more active, and not "adaptive", since the management of vegetation cover (including through logging, reforestation, fire prevention, etc.) is a fairly dynamic area of activity, and the main indicator of effectiveness measures are subject to the standard state registration of hunting species, as well as within the framework of monitoring of specially protected natural areas. The results of active measures to protect or change the elements of the spatial structure of the vegetation cover are mainly aimed at reducing fragmentation, increasing the connectivity of key habitats [9], ensuring the diversity of succession stages, and simulating the regimes of natural disturbances during forest management.

In the Abay region of Kazakhstan, there are a number of problems associated with forest management. Here are some of them:

– Illegal logging: One of the main problems is illegal logging of trees. Illegal logging is often carried out without permits and outside the control of government agencies. This leads to illegal enrichment and degradation of forest resources, as well as the violation of the ecological balance.

– Desertification and soil erosion: Due to the poor management of forest resources, there is a risk of desertification and soil erosion. Improper logging and lack of measures to conserve soil and natural resources

lead to the loss of soil fertility and the destruction of the ecosystem.

– Fires: Fires are a serious problem in the forests of the Abai region. Often they arise due to careless handling of fire, illegal logging and misuse of forest land. Fires lead to immature felling, destruction of ecosystems, loss of biodiversity and threat to human life and health.

– Inadequate Governance and Control: Insufficient governance and control by the state and the absence of effective monitoring and control mechanisms are a serious problem. Insufficient funding and limited resources lead to a lack of ability to control and regulate forest use, which encourages illegal practices.

Solving these problems requires an integrated approach and the inclusion of various parties: government agencies, local communities, academic researchers and public organizations. It is necessary to improve legislation, strengthen control and monitoring, conduct educational programs and develop sustainable forest management practices.

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